

Interview framework – Aasis rating pilot

Henna Suuronen, supervisor Anna von Zansen, University of Helsinki

*Note: Original interview framework was in Finnish, translated for research purposes.
(31.10.2024)*

1. Background questions

1.1 Rater ID

1.2 Consent for recording and storing the interview on the University of Helsinki computer -> transcription anonymously (data will be recorded, transcribed and recordings will be destroyed. Transcripts without direct identifiers such as names will be permanently stored in the Language Bank). If transcription tools are used, the Aasis Privacy Policy will be followed (e.g. automatic speech recognition using equipment provided by partner universities, data will not be sent outside the EU).

1.3 How did you feel about the pilot rating? In general, what was your overall impression on participating in the pilot and rating the oral interaction? (icebreaker/leading question)

1.4 How did you work during the rating process? Did you use an external screen or a laptop? How and at what point did you open the video/scale pdf/Webropol form?

1.5 You were given 4 h to complete the assessments. Was this time sufficient?

This interview consists of three main parts: the assessment of the oral interaction, the piloted criteria, and the automated assessment. In addition, if there is time, I will ask questions related to the tasks to be assessed.

2. Rating of oral interaction

The automatic assessment to be developed in the Aasis project will help learners to practice speaking Finnish and could, for example, help them to integrate better into Finnish higher education and working life.

2.1 What is the first thing that comes to your mind when talking about oral interaction? What does it include?

2.2 What verbal and non-verbal features do you consider important in assessment of oral interaction? *[If not coming up, give examples: body language (gestures, facial expressions, eye contact), use of extralinguistic speech sounds (e.g. "sh" as a sign of silence), voice quality (e.g. harsh or breathy), pitch (e.g. whining), loudness (e.g. whispering), speech duration (silences, overlapping speech), speech alternation?]*

2.3 Can you think of anything else you would like to say about the rating of oral interaction?

3. Piloted criteria

The criteria are displayed during the questions and I indicate which part of the criteria is being discussed at any given time.

3.1 What did you think of the holistic assessment of skills in dialogue performances? How did the scale work?

3.2 What did you think of the analytical scales for linguistic features (range, fluency, accuracy, pronunciation, interaction) in the assessment of dialogue performance?

3.3 What did you think of the non-verbal scale for assessing dialogue performance?

3.4 Did the absence of a non-verbal feature in the speech sample have any impact on the assessment of non-verbal features?

3.5 Do you consider this to be a comprehensive set of criteria for assessing oral interaction? Would you change any of the criteria and do you think any aspect is missing? *[I will specify if necessary: what is missing/is it comprehensive enough, verbal vs non-verbal? What would you remove/add to the criteria?]*

3.6 What *[other]* challenges do you see in the criteria?

3.7 Which sub-criteria of the analytical criteria would you emphasise in the assessment of oral interaction and why?

3.8 Did you find it difficult or easy to use the criteria?

3.9 Did you find that the criteria were suitable or too many?

3.10 Did you feel that the criteria were appropriate and meaningful?

3.11 Can you think of anything else you would like to say about the pilot rating criteria?

4. Automatic assessment and automatic feedback to the learner

The tool to be developed in the Aasis project will provide feedback to the learner on verbal and non-verbal aspects of their speech performance. The feedback will help the learner to practice speaking Finnish and could, for example, help them to integrate better into Finnish higher education and working life. (I will also explain, if necessary, that an automatic assessment tool was already developed in Digitala, so this is not completely impossible, but it did not include interaction assessment).

4.1 What kind of automatic feedback should be given to students based on dialogue performance? [*specify piloted criteria, non-verbal and verbal features if necessary*]

4.2 What do you think the feedback page seen by the learner should look like? (What should it contain to make the automated assessment as supportive as possible for the learner?)

4.3 What do you think about the automatic assessment provided by the machine in relation to the assessment provided by the human rater? [*Would it be complementary to the human rater's assessment? What is new/additional? What might be missing?*]

4.4 What could be the advantages and benefits of an automated assessment tool for oral interaction?

4.5 What are the potential disadvantages of an automated assessment tool for oral interaction?

4.6 In which situations would/should the use of an automated oral assessment tool be appropriate?

4.7 Can you think of anything else you would like to say about the automatic assessment tool?

5. If there is time

5.1 Which tasks do you think should be used to assess the oral interaction in relation to the project rating criteria?

5.2 What do you think about the tasks in Aasis [2 important place 3 introductory dialogue 4 everyday situations (customer and customer service representative) 5 negotiation tools]?

5.3 Can you think of anything else about the rating of the oral interaction that I did not ask?